

MESO SCALE ANALYSIS OF 2D GLASS WOVEN PREFORMS UNDER COMPACTION

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1. Introduction

The use of dry woven fabrics is becoming popular for structural composites as fabrics are easy to handle and drape, and reduce manufacturing costs. Resulting textile composites are damage tolerant due to interlacement between the tows. For the composite manufacturing a number of different techniques are being employed amongst which Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) and Vacuum Infusion (VI) are the most common. In all these manufacturing processes the dry preform is compacted to a certain level of pressure.

Compaction of the preform changes the yarn tow waviness which in turn changes the mechanical properties of the composites[1]. Compaction of the preform also effects its permeability[2]. This change in permeability is mainly considered due to inter-tow voids or resin channels reduction and only a negligible effect is due to intra-tow voids [2].

Additionally in multilayer fabrics the nesting of the layers effects the permeability [3].The nesting of the layers in the multilayer stack is also an important parameter deciding the preform thickness and the fibre volume fraction of the preform [4] ,The nesting effect was studied on the permeability of the woven fabrics by various researchers [3, 5, 6] , It was observed by Hoes that nesting is a major source of variation in experimentally determined permeabilities [7]. nesting has been calculated in terms of nesting factor [8] and nesting coefficient [9].

Here in this study the meso-structure of the 2D woven preform, single layer and stack of six and ten layers has been investigated. Different parameters including yarn waviness, nesting of the layers and the effect of the layer nesting on the resin channels has been studied under *in-situ* compressive loading using X-ray computed tomography (CT). Nesting factors (NF) has been calculated from mechanical test results and compared with nesting factors calculated from tomographic images. For the meso-structure analysis of fabric samples, the dry preform was compressed between two clear polycarbonate plates and scanned by computed tomography (CT).

2 Material & Experimental details

The material used was E-glass plain woven fabric with a warp density of 4.8/cm and weft density 4.4/cm. The warp and weft count was 660 Tex.

Mechanical testing for single layer and multilayer dry preform was performed using Instron 5569 testing system. The load cell capacity was 5kN and the machine speed during testing was 1mm/min, the area of the sample was 15 cm² and the area of the top and the bottom platens was 45 cm². Normally two test methods are used for the compression testing of the woven preforms 1) dynamic compression test method 2) static/step compression test method. In the dynamic testing method, the machine is continuously moved to the final load without any stop/hold in-between so that a continuous curve is obtained for pressure thickness values as shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Typical pressure thickness curve for dynamic loading

In static or step compression method, the machine is moved to the desired pressure or thickness and stopped there for a certain time before proceeding to the next position. Due to the creeping behavior of the fibers, fibers tend to relax and rearrange themselves under pressure, so either pressure drops to maintain a constant thickness or thickness drops to maintain a constant pressure. To maintain the pressure or thickness constant a certain time is given to the fibers to relax so that there is no further reduction in thickness or pressure. In this testing method, a step curve is achieved rather than a continuous curve for thickness or pressure against time (Fig.2).

In the present work, the static test method was used for compression testing of the fabric instead of dynamic method and load hold method was adopted in which machine was moved to the desired constant load and a hold of 5 minutes was given to the fibers to relax at each pressure level, the thickness was initially decreased and then it was stabilized with in this five minutes time.

Fig.2. Thickness, time curve for static loading

This five minutes hold time was considered adequate for this type of loading [10]. At each loading point the final thickness value was recorded.

Fig. 3. Instron compression set up

For meso-structural analysis of the dry preform, a compression rig was developed (Fig.4) to compress the fabric *in-situ* in the tomography machine. The rig consists of two clear polycarbonate plates 60x35x12 mm in length, width and thickness direction respectively. Two thickness gauges of known thickness were

placed on either side of the plate and two side screws were used to compress the plates from both sides. The fabric was placed between these two plates and was compressed to a known thickness by tightening the side screws after putting the thickness gauges on either side. The gauge thickness was decided according to the pressure level required and the thickness values against different pressures were taken from the pressure thickness curve obtained during compression testing of the preform.

Fig.4 Compression set up for *in-situ* loading

Fig. 5.Compression rig and the tomography set up.

Meso-structure of the tow and the resin channels was investigated using scanned samples of woven preform by x-ray computed tomography under *in-situ* compressive loading.

The fabric specimens were scanned on a Nikon Metrology 225/320 kV Custom Bay system at the Henry Moseley X-ray Imaging Facility in The University of Manchester. The system was equipped with a 225 kV static multi-metal anode source (Cu, Mo, Ag, and W) with a minimum focal spot size of 3 μm and a Perkin Elmer 2000 \times 2000 pixels 16-bit amorphous silicon flat panel detector. Scanning was performed with a silver target using a voltage of 85 kV and a current of 115 μA . The data acquisition was carried out with an exposure time of 1000 ms, the number of projections was set to 3142 and the number of frames per projection was 1. The volume was reconstructed at full resolution with a voxel size of 13.2 μm along the x , y , and z directions. Image analysis was performed using Avizo® Fire version 7.0.1 software. Each volume was cropped and a non-local means filter was applied to reduce image noise in each dataset.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Macro-deformation

The compaction of single layer and multilayer fabrics was performed on Instron testing machine as discussed earlier. The average layer thickness results are presented in Fig.6. The graph shows that the average layer thickness of single layer is more compared to six and ten layers stack, the reason is that the nesting of layers in multilayer stack results in reduced stack thickness which effects the average layer thickness. Also in case of multilayer stack, the average layer thickness of the six layer stack is higher than average layer thickness of ten layer stack, again the nesting of the layers results in reduced stack thickness in ten layer compared to six layers.

Fig.6.Average layer thickness of different layers plotted against pressure

3.2 Meso-deformation

The tomographic images obtained for single layer and for stack of six layers are shown in Fig.7,8 and Fig.9 respectively. Fig 10 shows the 3D view of reconstructed single layer using avizo software. The obtained images were studied for meso-structure using avizo software and yarn waviness and nesting was calculated using measure software.

Fig.7.Weft cross section of single layer

Fig.8.Weft cross section of six layers stack

Fig.9.Weft cross section of ten layers stack

Fig.10.Reconstructed single layer fabric

3.2.1 Yarn waviness

Due to interlacement of warp and weft yarns, a certain amount of waviness is imparted to the warp and weft yarns in fabrics. This waviness is termed as yarn crimp. Due to this yarn crimp, the length of the yarn in the fabric is more than the length of the fabric. Yarn crimp is calculated by using the following equation.

$$C\% = \frac{(L-P)}{L} * 100 \quad (1)$$

Where P and L are actual yarn length and crimp yarn length respectively (Fig.11).

Fig.11.Yarn waviness

The yarn waviness results are presented in Fig.12 and Fig.13.

Fig.12. Warp yarn crimp % of different layers

Fig.13. Weft yarn crimp % of different layers

During this study, it was observed that there was a higher crimp % age in the warp yarns compared to the weft yarns for both single and multilayer fabrics at a pressure of 100 kPa. The reason might be different tensions on warp and weft yarns during weaving process which resulted in different crimps in warp and weft yarns. After increase in pressure from 100 kPa to 300 kPa, the crimp in the warp yarns reduced and there was an increase in the crimp of the weft yarns. This phenomenon is know as crimp balancing in which on application of pressure,

crimp decreases in high crimped yarn and increases in low crimped yarn in case when the both yarns have different level of crimps before application of pressure. This phenomenon was discussed in detail by Potluri et al [8]. Also it was noted that the crimp % age in the multilayer fabrics was higher than the single layer fabric, the cause was the nesting of the layers in the multilayer stack , which was resulting in less crimp break in multilayer stack compared to the single layer. Also it was noted that in the multilayer stack, the yarn crimp was lesser at places where the yarn layers were sitting exactly upon each other with out nesting and the crimp was higher at those positions where the layer nesting was higher which shows the yarn crimp is highly influenced by nesting of the fabric layers.

3.2.2 Nesting of layers

Layer nesting is the term used for the multilayer fabric stacks. When the layers are compressed together, the “hills” and “valleys” of two adjacent layers nest one into another reducing the total thickness of the stack than the individual layer thickness and the phenomenon is termed as layer nesting [9].

The nesting of the layers is calculated in terms of nesting factor using the equation.

$$NF = Ts / \sum_1^n T_i \quad (2)$$

Where NF is the nesting factor, Ts is the stack thickness and T_i is the individual layer thickness. Higher the nesting factor, lesser will be nesting and vice versa. In case the the thickness of the individual layer is equal to H (Fig. 14a) , the nesting factor will be one. If the layers sit upon each other with out nesting (Fig. 14b) and the thickness of the two layers stack will be equal to sum of individual layer thickness. But when the layers shift and come closer to each other the nesting factor will be less than one and the thickness of the stack will be lesser than the sum of the thickness of the

individual layers by a factor “N”, where N is the nesting of the layers (Fig. 14c)

Fig.14. Single layer thickness (a), two layers thickness with out nesting (b) two layers thickness with nesting

Here in this study, the nesting of the layers was calculated for stacks of six and ten layers using mechanical testing and computed tomography results. In mechanical method, the single layer and the stack of six and ten layers were calculated using instron testing machine results and nesting factor was calculated using equation 2. In tomography method, the single layer thickness was calculated from individual layer thickness with in the stack and again using the equation 2, the nesting factors were calculated . It was seen that the nesting factors calculated for ten layers stack were lesser than the six layer stacks, In addition, the nesting factors from mechanical test results were higher than the nesting factors calculated from tomographic images (Fig 15), the reason was the single layer thickness calculated from stack of six and ten layers in tomography images was higher than the single layer results calculated from mechanical testing(Fig 16).

Fig.15. Nesting factor (NF) for different layers

The higher nesting in the ten layers was resulting in lower stack thickness of the ten layers compared to the six layers stack. The higher nesting of the layers give rise to increased fibre volume fraction of the preform and the composite so for making accurate simulation tools for fibre volume fractions, the nesting of the layers needs to be taken into account and the tomography can be used as a tool to calculate accurate nesting of the layers compared to mechanical test results which only give average nesting results whereas from the tomographic images, the local nesting can also be measured at different slices with in the fabric stack.

Fig.15. Single layer thickness from mechanical testing and tomography analysis

3.2.3 Nesting and inter-tow voids

The inter-tow voids or the resin channels in the stack of six and ten layers were also observed and the effect of nesting was studied on the resin channels. Both six and ten layer stacks were studied at different slices to investigate the effect of layer nesting on the resin channels. It was observed that the inter-tow voids were higher in the regions where the layers were sitting exactly upon each other with out nesting and the minimum channels were present at points where the layers were nesting with each other (Fig. 16). The channel size was found to be highly dependent on layer nesting. The size of the channels at the points with no nesting was up to 0.27 mm^2 compared to the nested region channel size where even no channels were present in perfect nesting situation. The behaviour of the channels was same for six and ten layers stacks for nesting and non nested cases. It can be seen from the Fig. 16 , the upper layers which are sitting upon each other with out nesting have big gaps/channels, compared to bottom layers with nesting which have minimum gaps for resin flow. The yarn packing increased with nesting in the lower layers.

Fig.16. Resin channels with nesting and non nesting of layers in ten layer stack

4 Conclusions

In this work, plain woven glass fabric samples of single layer and stack of six and ten layers were studied under *in-situ* compressive loading using computed tomography (CT). Different parameters including yarn waviness, nesting of the layers and its effect on inter-tow voids were investigated. It was observed that there is lower crimp reduction in multilayer stacks compared to single layer at same compaction pressures. Also there is less reduction in average layer thickness in multilayer stacks than the single layer as shown by CT results. The nesting of the layers increases with increase in number of layers with in stack. Also the nesting of the layers results in smaller resin channels giving minimum passage for resin flow. Over all the nesting of the layers is the main phenomenon effecting the layer thickness, tow waviness and the resin channels in the multilayer stacks.

References

- [1] B. Yang , V.Kozey , S.Adanur , S.Kumar "Bending, compression, and shear behavior of woven glass fiber–epoxy composites". Composites Part B: Engineering, 31(8):715-21, 2000.

- [2] B. Yu, L. James " *A simplified in-plane permeability model for textile fabrics*". Polymer Composites.;21(5):660-85. 2000
- [3] M. Grujicic, K. Chittajallu, S. Walsh " *Effect of shear, compaction and nesting on permeability of the orthogonal plain-weave fabric preforms*" Materials Chemistry and Physics.;86(2-3):358-69. 2004
- [4] B. Chen, T. Chou " *Compaction of woven-fabric preforms: nesting and multi-layer deformation*" Composites Science and Technology.;60(12-13):2223-31. 2000
- [5] M. Senoguz, F. Dungan, A. Sastry, J. Klamo. " *Simulations and experiments on low-pressure permeation of fabrics: Part II – The variable gap model and prediction of permeability*". Journal of Composite Materials.;35(14):1285-322. 2001
- [6] F. Dungan, M. Senoguz, A. Sastry, D. Faillaci " *Simulations and experiments on low-pressure permeation of fabrics: Part I-3D modeling of unbalanced fabric*" Journal of Composite Materials.;35(14):1250-84. 2001
- [7] K. Hoes, D. Dinescu, H. Sol, R.S. Parnas, S. Lomov " *Study of nesting induced scatter of permeability values in layered reinforcement fabrics*" Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing.;35(12):1407-18. 2004
- [8] P. Potluri, T.V. Sagar " *Compaction modelling of textile preforms for composite structures*" Composite Structures.;86(1-3):177-85. 2008
- [9] S.V. Lomov, L. Gorbatikh, Z. Kotanjac, V. Koissin, M. Houle, O. Rochez " *Compressibility of carbon woven fabrics with carbon nanotubes/nanofibres grown on the fibres*" Composites Science and Technology.;71(3):315-25. 2011
- [10] Y. Kim, S. McCarthy, J. Fanucci. " *Compressibility and relaxation of fiber reinforcements during composite processing*". Polymer Composites.;12(1):13-9. 1991